

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- Si K

C K_ROI (110)

O K_ROI (28)

Si K_ROI (53)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 9.17 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	93.4	0.00	96.3	13679.7	5.6
O K	2.2	0.01	1.7	504.0	8.8
Si K	4.4	0.01	1.9	859.3	5.7